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RESEARCH METHODOLOGY: SAMPLING &DATA ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

The process used to collect information and data for the purpose of making business decisions. The methodology may include publication research, interviews, surveys and other research techniques, and could include both present and historical information.

Data Analysis

Data analysis is the process of systematically examining data with the purpose of spotlighting useful information. Data analysis is the foundation of scientific research.

Qualitative or Quantitative Data

The type of data you collect depends on the question you want to answer and your resources. As discussed in Module Four (click here to review this module), there are two types of data: qualitative and quantitative. Both types of data have strengths and limitations and may be appropriate for different settings, evaluation designs, and evaluation questions.

Qualitative data consist of words and narratives. The analysis of qualitative data can come in many forms including highlighting key words, extracting themes, and elaborating on concepts. Quantitative data are numerical information, the analysis of which involves statistical techniques. The type of data you collect guides the analysis process.

Qualitative Data

Quantitative Data

Types of Variables

In the last section you reviewed qualitative and quantitative data. Surveys primarily collect quantitative data, so the rest of this module will focus on analyzing quantitative data. Surveys can

contain many kinds of questions; these questions are often called variables. There are some basic types of variables. It is important to understand the different types of variables, because the type of variable can lead to different kinds of data and guide your analysis. The following are types of variables:

There are three types of categorical variables:

Binary

Practical

Ordinal

There are two types of continuous variables:

Interval

Ratio

Statistical Tests:

There is a wide range of statistical tests. The decision of which statistical test to use depends on the research design, the distribution of the data, and the type of variable. In general, if the data is normally distributed, you will choose from parametric tests. If the data is non-normal, you will choose from the set of non-parametric tests. Below is a table listing just a few common statistical tests and their use

Type of Test

Correlational

These tests look for an association between variables

Pearson correlation

Tests for the strength of the association between two continuous variables

Spearman correlation

Tests for the strength of the association between two ordinal variables (does not rely on the assumption of normally distributed data)

Chi-square

Tests for the strength of the association between two categorical variables

Comparison of Means

look for the difference between the means of variables

Paired T-test

Tests for the difference between two related variables

Independent T-test

Tests for the difference between two independent variables

ANOVA

Tests the difference between group means after any other variance in the outcome variable is accounted for

Regression

assess if change in one variable predicts change in another variable

Simple regression

Tests how change in the predictor variable predicts the level of change in the outcome variable

Multiple regression

Tests how change in the combination of two or more predictor variables predict the level of change in the outcome variable

Non-parametric

used when the data does not meet assumptions required for parametric tests

Wilcoxon rank-sum test

Tests for the difference between two independent variables—takes into account magnitude and direction of difference

Wilcoxon sign-rank test

Tests for the difference between two related variables—takes into account the magnitude and direction of difference

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis is used in order to gain an understanding of a larger population by analysing

the information of a sample. Statistical analysis allows inferences to be drawn about target markets, consumer cohorts and the general population by expanding findings appropriately to predict the behaviour and characteristics of the many based on the few.

Data analysis is the process of inspecting, presenting and reporting data in a way that is useful to non-technical people. Because data is next to useless if it can't be understood by the decision-makers who need to use it, data analysts act as translators between the numbers and figures and the people who need to know about them.

Sampling Methods

Definitions

Sampling is the process of selecting a representative group from the population under study.

The target population is the total group of individuals from which the sample might be drawn.

A sample is the group of people who take part in the investigation. The people who take part are referred to as "participants".

Generalisability refers to the extent to which we can apply the findings of our research to the target population we are interested in.

The Purpose of Sampling

In psychological research we are interested in learning about large groups of people who all have something in common. We call the group that we are interested in studying our 'target population'.

Sampling methods are used to select a sample from within a general population. Proper sampling methods are important for eliminating bias in the selection process. They can also allow for the reduction of cost or effort in gathering samples. Common methods of sampling include simple random sampling (completely random selection from the population), systematic sampling (ordering the population and selecting at regular intervals), stratified sampling (splitting the population into

sampling target population

It is more or less impossible to study every single person in a target population so psychologists select a sample or sub-group of the population that is likely to be representative of the target population we are interested in.

Sampling Method

1. Random Sampling

Everyone in the entire target population has an equal chance of being selected. Random samples require a way of naming or numbering the target population and then using some type of raffle method to choose those to make up the sample. Random samples are the best method of selecting your sample from the population of interest. The advantages are that your sample should represent the target population and eliminate sampling bias, but the disadvantage is that it is very difficult to achieve (i.e. time, effort and money).

2. Stratified Sampling

The researcher identifies the different types of people that make up the target population and works out the proportions needed for the sample to be representative. A list is made of each variable (e.g. IQ, gender etc.) which might have an effect on the research. For example, if we are interested in the money spent on books by undergraduates, then the main subject studied may be an important variable.

3. Opportunity Sampling

Uses people from target population available at the time and willing to take part. It is based on convenience. An opportunity sample is obtained by asking members of the population of interest if they would take part in your research. An example would be selecting a sample of students from those coming out of the library.

4. Systematic Sampling

Chooses subjects in a systematic (i.e. orderly / logical) way from the target population, like every nth participant on a list of names. To take a systematic sample, you list all the members of the population, and then decided upon a sample you would like. By dividing the number of people in the population by the number of people you want in your sample, you get a number we will call n.

Sampling In Research

This tutorial is a discussion on sampling in research it is mainly designed to equip beginners with knowledge on the general issues on sampling that is the purpose of sampling in research, dangers of sampling and how to minimize them, types of sampling and guides for deciding the sample size. For a clear flow of ideas, a few definitions of the terms used are given.

TYPES OF SAMPLES

There are three primary kinds of samples: the convenience, the judgement sample, and the random sample. They differ in the manner in which the elementary units are chosen.

The convenient sample

A convenience sample results when the more convenient elementary units are chosen from a population for observation.

The judgement sample

A judgement sample is obtained according to the discretion of someone who is familiar with the relevant characteristics of the population.

The random sample

This may be the most important type of sample. A random sample allows a known probability that each elementary unit will be chosen. For this reason, it is sometimes referred to as a probability sample. This is the type of sampling that is used in lotteries and raffles.

TYPES OF RANDOM SAMPLES

Simple Random Sample

A simple random sample is obtained by choosing elementary units in such a way that each unit in the population has an equal chance of being selected. A simple random sample is free from sampling bias. However, using a random number table to choose the elementary units can be cumbersome. If the sample is to be collected by a person untrained in statistics, then instructions may be misinterpreted and selections may be made improperly. Instead of using a list of random numbers, data collection can be simplified by selecting say every 10th or 100th unit after the first unit has been chosen randomly as discussed below. Such a procedure is called systematic random sampling.

Systematic Random Sample

A systematic random sample is obtained by selecting one unit on a random basis and choosing additional elementary units at evenly spaced intervals until the desired number of units is obtained.

Stratified Sample

A stratified sample is obtained by independently selecting a separate simple random sample from each population stratum. A population can be divided into different groups that may be based on

some characteristic or variable like income of education.

Cluster Sample

A cluster sample is obtained by selecting clusters from the population on the basis of simple random sampling. The sample comprises a census of each random cluster selected..

SAMPLE SIZE

Before deciding how large a sample should be, you have to define your study population. For example, all children below age three in Tomkin`s County. Then determine your sampling frame which could be a list of all the children below three as recorded by Tomkin`s County. You can then struggle with the sample size.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be said that using a sample in research saves mainly on money and time, if a suitable sampling strategy is used, appropriate sample size selected and necessary precautions taken to reduce on sampling and measurement errors, then a sample should yield valid and reliable information. Details on sampling can be obtained from the references included below and many other books on statistics or qualitative research which can be found in libraries.

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